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USE OF AUTHOR'S PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MEDICINE

Alimjanova Dilbar Negmatovna

Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Amridinov Shavkat Alisherovich

Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Abstract: Currently, interest in innovations in education is not diminishing; on the contrary, it is growing. Modern education in Uzbekistan faces the necessity of continuously updating teaching methods and employing innovative approaches in pedagogical practice. One of the key aspects is the development and application of author's technologies in pedagogical disciplines. This article discusses the theoretical analysis of key concepts such as "innovative technologies" and "author's pedagogical innovations" in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: innovative technologies, author's technologies, educational process.

Introduction

In today's world, education plays a key role in shaping the future of the nation. In Uzbekistan, the government pays special attention to the development of education and the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies. Author's pedagogical technologies are becoming increasingly popular among teachers and education specialists.

Modern education in Uzbekistan faces the necessity of constantly updating teaching methods and adopting innovative approaches in pedagogical practice. One of the key aspects is the development and application of author's technologies in the teaching of pedagogical disciplines. This helps to enhance the effectiveness of the educational process and align with the contemporary quality standards of education.

In Uzbekistan, author's pedagogical technologies are actively being implemented in both school and higher education. Educators develop their own teaching methodologies, considering the specifics of the study group, the individual characteristics of students, and the current educational demands. This enables the creation of unique educational programs tailored to the specific needs of students.

Author's technologies in pedagogy represent innovative methodologies developed by educators based on personal experience, research, and analysis of modern trends in education. These technologies allow the personalization of the educational process by taking into account students' individual characteristics and creating comfortable conditions for the assimilation of knowledge.

Literature Review

Author's pedagogical technologies represent specific methodologies and approaches developed by individual educators or educational institutions. They aim to enhance the efficiency of the educational process, foster critical thinking, promote a creative approach to learning, and develop key competencies in students.

In the works of renowned Uzbek researchers (N. Azizkhodzhaeva, N. Muslimov, U. Inoyatov), such classifications are provided and considered as methodological systems and concepts.

According to N. Saidakhmedov, the distinctive features of pedagogical technology are:

— Universality, meaning independence from content (informational filling or the content of the academic "subject");

— Reproducibility, meaning independence from the teacher's qualification and personality, the personalities of students, or the wealth or poverty of the school;

— Replicability, meaning the ability to reproduce results;

— Manageability of the educational process based on an algorithmized system of pedagogical procedures;

— Systematic selection of components.

The absence of at least one of these features excludes the methodology from the category of technologies.

Theoretical Foundations

One of the main goals of author's pedagogical technologies is the development of students' creative thinking. Educators encourage students to work independently, seek non-standard solutions to problems, and develop creativity and innovative thinking. This contributes to fostering personal activity and responsibility for one's education.

Additionally, author's pedagogical technologies contribute to creating a favorable educational environment. Teachers actively use interactive teaching methods, game-based work, project-based tasks, and other innovative approaches, making learning more engaging and effective.

One example of successful implementation of author's pedagogical technologies in Uzbekistan is the "Innovative School" project. As part of this project, teachers develop and implement their own educational programs using modern information technologies, interactive teaching methods, and other innovative approaches. This creates conditions for the development of each student's talents and abilities while also increasing motivation for learning.

Practical Application

Teaching tools in pedagogical disciplines include various methods and techniques aimed at activating students' learning activities. Among them are:

1. **Interactive lectures and seminars.** Using interactive teaching methods helps stimulate students' activity, develop critical thinking, and contribute to a deep understanding of educational material.

2. **Project-based activities.** Involving students in project work in pedagogical disciplines fosters the development of creative abilities, independence, and communication skills.

3. **Use of modern information and communication technologies.** Utilizing computer programs, internet resources, and multimedia materials makes learning more visual, accessible, and interesting for students.

4. **Role-playing and business games.** This method allows students to practice decision-making, teamwork, and conflict management skills, which are important aspects of professional teacher training.

5. **Individual consultations and tutoring.** Holding individual sessions with a teacher allows for addressing the unique needs of students, helping them resolve educational challenges, and developing professional competencies.

Effectiveness Analysis

The analysis of the effectiveness of author's technologies is based on comparing educational outcomes before and after their implementation. Qualitative and quantitative research methods are used,

including surveys, interviews, observations, and academic performance analysis. The results show that the use of author's technologies not only improves academic performance but also develops interpersonal and communication skills, as well as students' adaptation to the conditions of the modern educational and professional world.

In the new paradigm of improving the training of highly qualified specialists, a significant issue is the implementation of author's pedagogical technologies into the educational process.

Development Prospects

Further research in the field of author's technologies in pedagogical disciplines could focus on the following areas:

1. **Development of comprehensive evaluation models.** Creation of universal tools and criteria for measuring the impact of author's technologies on the educational process and learning outcomes.
2. **Study of long-term effects.** Conducting extended research to evaluate the impact of author's technologies on the professional development and career growth of graduates.
3. **Development of integration strategies.** Identifying the most effective approaches to the implementation and integration of author's technologies into existing educational programs and courses.

Conclusion

Thus, author's pedagogical technologies play an important role in the modern education system of Uzbekistan. They contribute to improving the quality of education, developing students' personalities, and shaping competitive professionals. The introduction of innovative approaches into the educational process is one of the priority directions for the development of education in Uzbekistan.

Research on the application of author's technologies in pedagogical disciplines demonstrates the significant potential of these innovations for improving the quality and efficiency of the educational process. The benefits, such as personalized learning, increased motivation, and student engagement, as well as the development of critical thinking and creative abilities, highlight the importance of integrating modern technologies into educational practices.

However, despite the clear advantages, there are also certain limitations, including resource requirements, the need for teacher professional development, and potential resistance to change. These challenges require careful consideration and the development of effective strategies to overcome them.

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